

Integrated Network Design and Demand Estimation for Advanced Air Mobility Using an Extended Multiple-Allocation p-Hub Median Framework

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Abstract—It is essential to take the emerging transportation mode, Advanced Air Mobility (AAM), into transportation planning for developing a safe and efficient integrated multimodal transportation system. However, there are many operational uncertainties of AAM due to technological advancements, industry development, and regulatory establishment. Instead of operational details, e.g., fleet planning, eVTOL scheduling, and passenger assignment, transportation planners and policymakers want to know potential vertiport locations and the number and spatial distribution of travelers shifting from driving to using AAM services. To address these needs, our study examines the AAM integrated network design and demand estimation from a planning perspective. Given a traffic analysis zone (TAZ)-level origin and destination (OD) demand matrix, we propose an Extended Multiple Allocation p-Hub Median Problem (E-MApHMP) to determine optimal vertiport locations and estimate the shifted demand simultaneously. The objective of the mathematical programming is to minimize system-wide generalized travel cost, or, equivalently, to maximize the savings in generalized travel cost from shifting ground demand to air. A case study of Tampa Bay Region Plus (TBR+) involves 1,526 TAZs across seven counties, assuming each TAZ could potentially host one vertiport. Given the complexity of the problem, we developed a three-part chromosome-structured Genetic Algorithm (GA) with local search strategies to solve it efficiently. The traveler and socioeconomic data for this paper were drawn from a travel demand model developed for western Florida, US. Across multiple problem instances with fixed initial seeds, the proposed genetic algorithm (GA) consistently outperformed other metaheuristic algorithms and the Gurobi solver in terms of solution quality and computational efficiency. A factorial design sensitivity analysis was conducted to identify key parameters influencing AAM demand, the share of low-income travelers, and access and egress travel distances to vertiports. Results from the Type II ANOVA indicate that vertiport processing time, vertiport parking price, and the per-mile flying fee are the most significant factors affecting these outcomes.

Keywords: Urban Air Mobility (UAM), OpenSky, Travel Demand Modeling, Three-part Chromosome Genetic Algorithm, Factorial Design Sensitivity Analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced Air Mobility (AAM) is expected to be a safe and efficient travel mode that can be used to avoid surface congestion in urban areas, extend mobility to rural areas that lack transportation options, and expedite inter-city and long-distance intra-city travel. Air vehicles that could be used for AAM include short takeoff and landing (STOL), vertical takeoff and landing (VTOL), and conventional takeoff and landing (CTOL), which primarily run on electric or hybrid fuels. AAM requires vertiports as a place for passengers to board and deplane and passenger access vertiports via various ground transportation modes. One early stage AAM use case could be air taxi, an on-demand shared air mobility service. Such services could be offered by a sole operators and multiple operators. In a more mature market, while considering adding a facility node, business will consider the network of competitors and their possible responses.

As an emerging mode, however, there are many uncertainties in terms of technology advancement, industry development, and regulatory establishment. Instead of operational details, e.g., fleet planning, eVTOL scheduling, and passenger assignment, transportation planning society and policy makers more want to know potential vertiport locations and the number and spatial distribution of travelers shifting from driving to using AAM service, so that they could make decisions on resource allocation, and public funding investment for a safe and more efficient integrated multimodal transportation system. To respond to such needs, our study addresses the AAM integrated network design and demand estimation from planning perspective.

Significant efforts have been made to model and solve the AAM network design problem using optimization approaches to determine optimal vertiport locations. The optimization objectives vary, including

maximizing AAM demand, minimizing network cost, or maximizing the total profit of AAM service provider. While some studies focus solely on AAM network design, excluding access/egress links and competition with ground transportation, progress has been made in integrated AAM network design. Researchers have incorporated operational concepts such as fleet size, scheduling, vertiport siting, and demand estimation. However, two critical aspects remain unexplored: (1) Airspace Integration – Existing network design models do not incorporate airspace analysis to generate more accurate estimated flight time of AAM aircraft. Oversimplifying flight time can lead to distorted or suboptimal vertiport siting outcomes.; (2) Multimodal Integration & Real-World Scalability – Many existing network design studies focus solely on the air mode and overlook the critical air-ground connections. Evaluating AAM network design and demand estimation from a multimodal perspective with real-world problem sizes can provide more actionable insights for public agencies. Addressing these gaps will significantly increase the complexity of the problem, requiring efficient solution algorithms to generate comprehensive, decision-ready results for policymakers and transportation planners.

For AAM network design and demand estimation, input data may be either disaggregate—such as individual trip records from activity-based demand models or GPS traces—or aggregate, such as traffic analysis zone (TAZ)-level origin-destination flows that assume homogeneous travelers within each analysis zone. This study addresses the problem using aggregate input data. We assume that each TAZ contains at least one feasible candidate site for vertiport placement. The objective is not to pinpoint exact vertiport locations, but rather to identify a small subset of TAZs, selected from thousands across a region, that can best serve regional demand while simultaneously determining passenger allocations through vertiports and the associated ground access and egress travel.

Mathematically, we formulate this integrated AAM network design and demand estimation problem as an extended p-Hub median problem. In traditional p-Hub median formulations—whether used in logistics facility location or airline hub-spoke network design—demand is predefined and the objective is to minimize transportation costs. In contrast, our extended p-Hub median problem explicitly models competition between AAM (including access and

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews three key areas of literature related to integrated AAM network design and

egress components) and other transportation modes, with the goal of minimizing system-wide generalized transportation costs. Moreover, travel demand from a single TAZ may be distributed across multiple vertiport pairs, making this a multiple-allocation problem. We refer to the proposed formulation as the Extended Multiple Allocation p-Hub Median Problem (E-MApHMP).

This AAM network design problem is computationally intensive, and existing literature lacks efficient algorithms capable of solving large-scale instances as problem size increases [3]. To address this gap, we develop a novel Genetic Algorithm designed to effectively solve large-scale E-MApHMP problems, thereby advancing the methodological foundations of AAM network design.

The proposed modeling framework and solution algorithm were applied to a case study to determine optimal vertiport locations for the extended Tampa Bay Region (TBR+) and estimate the daily travel demand attracted to AAM. In the base scenario, the objective was to select 30 vertiports from 1,521 TAZs. Using an off-the-shelf Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP) solver (Gurobi), solving the problem with a 2.33% gap required 6,523 minutes. In contrast, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) produced a better solution in just 33.7 minutes, demonstrating significant computational efficiency. In the 2045-year scenario, 7,058 trips shift to AAM, representing 0.05% of total travel demand that could shift to AAM (but with a lower generalized cost than using AAM). Sensitivity analysis results indicate that this relatively low AAM mode share could increase to over 0.19% if certain factors favor AAM adoption, including number of vertiports, base air price (\$), air price per mile (\$ per mile), vertiport access parking price (\$), and vertiport processing time (minutes). A detailed discussion of the extensive sensitivity analysis based on factorial design results follows in later sections.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides background on AAM airspace corridors, AAM network design, and relevant GA approaches for solving AAM network problems. Section 3 presents the methodology for AAM airspace analysis, the E-MApHMP model, and the proposed GA. Section 4 discusses GA performance compared to the off-the-shelf MIP solver and E-MApHMP results under multiple scenarios. Section 5 concludes the paper and outlines future research directions.

demand estimation. Firstly, we reviewed public agency documents and research papers on AAM airspace planning and regulation. Then, we reviewed recent studies applying p-Hub median optimization to simultaneously design AAM networks and estimate

demand. This review was followed with a summary of research on GA-based approaches for solving multiple allocation p-Hub median problems. At the end of this section, we outline the main contributions of this paper in the context of existing literature.

2.1 AAM Airspace Analysis

The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) published the UAM Concept of Operations Version 2.0 in April 2023 [1]. As the concept continues to evolve, future versions are expected. The FAA concept of operation states that "No solutions, specific implementation methods, or detailed operational procedures are described in this document except for example purposes (i.e., operational scenarios)." The FAA concept is similar to that of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) [2]. Since available documents from NASA and the FAA do not enumerate specific design criteria for AAM airspace corridors (e.g., altitudes, airspace restrictions, etc.) or specify separation criteria (either between AAM vehicles, between AAM vehicles and conventional aircraft, or between AAM vehicles and Uncrewed Aircraft Systems (UAS)), further research is required in this area to establish AAM corridors properly.

Several authors have studied the NASA and the FAA concepts and conducted literature reviews and stakeholder interviews to provide deeper insights. Thippavong et al. [3] suggest that AAM routes could initially align with charted helicopter routes and Visual Flight Rules (VFR) flyways. Cohen et al. [4] conducted extensive interviews and workshops with stakeholders and experts to characterize the state of the industry and its potential evolution. Cohen says, "The ability for AAM to transition from either uncontrolled Class G airspace and/or AAM corridors to busy controlled airspace (i.e., Class B) without overwhelming ATC represents a key unresolved challenge." Lee et al. [5] describe several classes of new vehicles, including UAS, AAM, and high-altitude long endurance (HALE) aircraft operating in Class E airspace above Flight Level 600 (so-called Upper-E airspace). Verma et al. [6] studied the airspace in the Dallas-Ft. Worth area and designed AAM corridors that avoid today's busy traffic areas to minimize air traffic controller interactions with AAM pilots and operators. Verma et al. [6] applied a set of heuristics (including wake vortex separation minima) to historical aircraft track data to define the corridors. The corridor volumes were assumed to have a floor of 400 ft Above Ground Level (AGL) and a ceiling of 600 ft AGL, with all AAM flights operating at 500 ft AGL. The corridor width is 3,000 ft, with opposite-direction routes separated by 1,500 ft. Vascik [7] used Airport Surface Detection Equipment Model X (ASDE-X) surveillance data to study flight densities in

the Los Angeles area. He concluded that there are highly concentrated corridors of operations off the approach and departure ends of runways but that the remainder of the Class B airspace is sparsely utilized. Vascik proposed fine-scale Dynamic Flight Rules Areas (DFRA), which avoid major flight corridors, for AAM operations. After reviewing government and industry research on designing AAM corridors around the world, Bauranov and Rakas [8] state that corridor design that relies on current available technology is less likely attainable in the current stage of AAM development, meaning that moderate-structure AAM corridors based on layering, zoning, and safe corridors could facilitate early-stage eVTOL traffic.

Overall, airspace analysis for AAM is yet to be explored more, and in the current situation, we can infer that 1) AAM can take advantage of VFR routes, 2) AAM air routes should avoid airspace where commercial flight routes exist based on layering and zoning, 3) AAM trajectories should be between 500-3,000 ft AGL. Because of the large height of AAM airspace, we could divide the airspace based on the height into layers and grid each layer into smaller zones. Therefore, we can calculate the density of the flight traffic in the zone-layer cubic and specify the obstacle airspace. In this study, a zone-layer airspace structure will be applied to define the space used frequently by current air traffic activities. Furthermore, a visibility graph technique will be used to find shortest air path between vertiports by avoiding those airspace and other obstacles.

2.2 AAM Network Design

AAM network design has been studied in the last several years. Daskilewicz et al. [9] employed the basic binary integer programming to optimize vertiport locations, considering population data at the census tracts level and vertiport capacities. They utilized census data to identify commuting origins and destinations, applying an integer program to optimize vertiport locations for maximal time savings compared to car travel. Their study did not provide detailed optimization formulation to determine whether they considered access/egress links to the vertiports. Wu and Zhang [10] developed an integrated network design and mode choice modeling to determine the optimal location of vertiports and estimate shifted demand from existing ground transportation to AAM. They used individual traveler demand data simulated from an activity-based demand model and took the access/egress of vertiports into the calculation of generalized travel cost. They modeled the problem as a single-allocation p-Hub median problem with additional mode-choice constraints. Their findings show that people who shift to multimodal AAM could benefit from significant time savings; however, the

share of travelers choosing to shift is insignificant, given the baseline number of vertiports in the region and the pricing schemes assumed for the operations. In another study, Escribano Macias et al. [11] incorporated vehicle sizing into the vertiport location planning problem. They designed a feedback mechanism to capture the effect of vertiport placement and the number of pads per vertiport to minimize infrastructure costs. Their results show neglecting fleet sizing and vertiport congestion will result in an infeasible or underperforming AAM network. However, they did not consider that AAM vehicles and operational features have a significant amount of uncertainty at the current stage, and providing a comprehensive early-stage vertiport siting and demand estimation could be more beneficial for transportation planners. The main drawback of this study is that access/egress links for multimodal AAM are not considered in the modeling process. Yu et al. [12] developed a single allocation hub location problem to optimize vertiport location in a grid base transportation network. They incorporated the equilibrium principle for traffic assignments in their vertiport location problem to minimize air and ground transportation links traffic congestion. Chen et al. [13] proposed a single allocation vertiport selection model in the metropolitan area using a grid structure (demand was aggregated at grid cell level, and the hub was assumed to be located at the cell center). In their study, some grid cells were excluded from vertiport selection due to environmental, technical, or other reasons, but they did not consider airspace restrictions for eVTOL routing. However, both Yu et al. [12] and Chen et al. [13] did not consider the multiple allocation nature of the travelers' AAM routes and did not provide their modeling approach runtime performance for larger than 400 nodes or grids.

More studies that could be categorized into this group are available in the literature, including Rath and Chow [14], Shin et al. [15], and Kai et al. [16]. Based on the aggregated trips originated from taxi zones to three airports, Rath and Chow [14] developed a single allocation p-Hub median problem to find the vertiport locations. They solve the problem for two separate objectives: maximizing the choice-constrained (percentage of each OD passenger choosing AAM based on their utility) demand and profit. By turning a metropolitan area in South Korea into 40 district zones, Shin et al. [15] proposed another single allocation hub location problem with the objective to minimize risk of midair eVTOLs collision. In their study, Kai et al. [16] proposed an original model for optimizing vertiport numbers, locations, and capacities. Their model addressed the interaction between strategic planning, operational tactics, and consumer demand in AAM. Their mathematical formulation encapsulates a multinomial logit model to determine the AAM demand for each pair given a set of vertiports. The key

findings include the importance of centralized vertiport placement for efficient operations and the competitiveness of AAM in long-distance markets over alternatives like commuter rail and self-driving vehicles. However, their model is developed for operational level purposes and solely focuses on optimizing the total profit. In addition, the achieved results could differ if the airspace obstacles have been considered because their models have been applied to large urban areas that contain heavy commercial flight activities. Another drawback is that when their demand scaling factor increases, the runtime of their optimization method significantly increases to over 960 minutes.

Upon reviewing the existing literature on AAM network design, we found a lack of studies addressing the problem from a multimodal transportation perspective. The problem sizes in existing research are relatively small, and the outcomes are often not suitable for public agencies to use in transportation planning or evaluating the impacts of AAM integration with multimodal transportation systems. Additionally, no case studies in the current literature have considered air link network design or incorporated it into air travel time calculations.

2.3 Genetic Algorithms (GA) for AAM Network Design

GA is a metaheuristic algorithm applied to various problems in the literature, including the multiple allocation p-Hub median problems. Shin et al. [15] used a GA to solve a vertiport location optimization problem, and their algorithm had the worst optimal gap of 1.93%. Most recent research in the multiple allocation hub location problem uses two-part chromosome representation or encoding to store the solution information in the GA iterations [17-19]. The first part of the chromosome is a one-dimensional (1D) encoding of hub/vertiport locations. However, multiple designs of the two-dimensional (2D) matrix for the second part of the chromosome have been used: assignment of hubs to non-hubs, mode of transportation OD matrix, and direct links OD matrix.

An extended AAM network design problem should decide trips that shift ground transportation to AAM service, vertiport locations, and access/egress links for all shifted ODs to AAM (AAM trip route). The downside of GA proposed in the literature is that when the chromosome is two parts, information on access/egress links is lost in the chromosome. Additional algorithms, such as the A* algorithm [18], shortest path [20], or nearest vertiports [15], should be run during the GA to calculate the objective value of chromosomes. As the problem size increases, the A* and shortest path algorithms could face an increased GA runtime (we further discuss this in the result section). Connecting the non-vertiports to the closest

vertiports could be beneficial only for a single allocation variation and is not applicable to E-MApHMP. In addition, this approach does not take into account the whole OD trip cost and time. To overcome this downside, we propose a three-part chromosome structure and include a set of local neighborhood search strategies to improve the solution quality on each GA iteration. To the authors' knowledge, very few studies have developed a three-part chromosome structure for problems close to multiple allocation p-Hub problems. For example, Shang et al. [21] structured a three-part chromosome for the stochastic multi-modal hub location problem where each chromosome part encodes hubs and spokes, transportation mode, and direct links OD matrix. However, they solve the problem as a single allocation. In the AAM network, trips that start from an origin could be connected to multiple vertiports to go through the AAM network and reach their destination. Therefore, in this study, we proposed a three-part chromosome structure GA to capture the access/egress data within the chromosome.

2.4 Contribution of this study

Given the research gaps identified from the literature review, our study makes the following key contributions:

1. Airspace Analysis and Integrated AAM Network Design - We introduce a zone-layer structure to analyze airspace obstacles and design an AAM-integrated network, ensuring feasible and efficient air routes.
2. Multimodal Transportation Perspective with Multiple Allocation - To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to approach integrated AAM network design from a multimodal transportation planning perspective while incorporating multiple allocation for grid- or TAZ-level study units.
3. Realistic Problem Size and Comprehensive Planning Approach - Many existing studies either limiting candidate vertiport locations to under 100, selecting only a few dozen for the final solution, or aggregating large metropolitan areas and select fewer than 10 vertiports. These approaches may be too restrictive for short- to mid-term planning. Instead, we propose an AAM network design with realistic problem sizes to enable planning for different ranges and informed decision-making.
4. Novel Genetic Algorithm (GA) for Efficient Problem Solving - Our study is the first to propose a three-part chromosome structure GA for solving multiple allocation p-Hub median problems. We incorporate local neighborhood search strategies to enhance solution quality and computational efficiency, ensuring that large-scale AAM

network design problems can be solved in a timely manner.

3 PROBLEM DEFINITION AND RESEARCH APPROACH

The integrated AAM network design and demand estimation problem in this study is defined as follows. From a transportation planning and regulatory development perspectives, stakeholders seek to understand optimal vertiport locations for a given region and estimate potential trips shift from ground transportation to AAM, considering access and egress time and cost. The input data for this problem includes: (1) the TAZ-level origin-destination matrix; (2) the number of vertiports to be deployed; (3) AAM service pricing; (4) ground transportation costs and travel times between any OD pairs. It is assumed that vertiports can potentially be located at the centroid of each TAZ. To estimate air travel times, historical flight trajectory data is used for airspace analysis and the development of an airlink network connecting vertiport pairs. The objective is to determine the optimal vertiport locations to minimize the total generalized travel cost of all trips in the region. In other words, the goal is to maximize the saved generalized travel cost for trips shifting from ground to multimodal AAM. The calculation of generalized travel cost for multimodal AAM includes access to origin vertiport, process at origin vertiport, eVTOL flight from origin vertiport to destination vertiport, and egress from destination vertiport.

The research approach to solving the problem will be detailed in the following sections, along with describing a case study demonstrating the operability of the proposed methodology.

3.1 Case Study Region and Data Preparation

The case study area includes five counties in Florida Department of Transportation (FDOT) District 7 (Citrus, Hernando, Hillsborough, Pasco, and Pinellas) and two counties (Sarasota and Manatee) from District 1, given the close economic connections between these counties. For simplification, we call this study area, containing 1,521 TAZs, Tampa Bay Region Plus (TBR+).

Florida's passenger and freight traffic demand model is called the Florida Statewide Model (FLSWM), including 2015 baseline model and predicted 2045 model. The data derived from FLSWM include TAZ level origin and destination matrix, driving times and distances between TAZs, and median income of each TAZ. The median income is used for calculating the value of time (VOT) of travelers. by dividing zonal median incomes by annual work hours (2,080 hours). Since the incomes are from 2015, we adjust them to

2023 using a compounded CPI inflation rate of 30 percent based on the “Consumer Price Index Historical Tables for U.S. City Average” published by the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics.

The generalized cost of a transportation mode consists of two parts: the value of travel time and transportation cost. The value of travel time is calculated by multiplying passengers’ VOT by the total travel time. The total travel time for AAM includes access,

embarking, flight, disembarking, and egress time. For access and egress, our proposed optimization model takes transit and for-hire services into consideration. However, transit travel times between TAZs are not available from FLSWM. Following the existing literature, we estimate transit travel time by multiplying automobile travel time by a scaling factor of 2.6 [22]. The cost formulas and relevant parameters for different transportation modes in this study are listed in TABLE I.

TABLE I Pricing schemes for different transportation modes [10]

Mode	Cost Formula	Cost values (USD)
Private Car	Gasoline cost per mile \times trip distance + parking cost	Gasoline cost per mile = 0.15, Parking cost for median density areas = 10
For-hire Service	Base cost + (unit time cost \times trip time) + (unit distance cost \times trip distance)	Base cost = 2.3, unit time cost = 0.28, unit distance cost = 0.8
Transit	With transit pass	2
AAM flight	Base cost + (unit distance cost \times trip distance)	Base cost = 30, unit distance cost = 2

3.2 Airspace Analysis for AAM Airlink Network

To design the airline network for the case study region, we first analyze current aircraft operations using surveillance data. The primary source for this data is the OpenSky Network, a crowd-sourced archive of ADS-B and Mode S transponder messages transmitted by aircraft worldwide [26]. OpenSky Network is a community-based receiver network. To verify the quality of OpenSky surveillance data in the Tampa Bay Region, we obtain the daily operation data of Tampa International airport (TPA) from FAA Aviation System Performance Metrics (ASPM) database and compare the daily TPA arrivals from the ASPM and OpenSky database (see Figure 1). We then chose two days for further analysis: March 13, 2022, when TPA was operating in a north flow configuration, and March 18, 2022, when TPA was operating in a south flow configuration. These are the busiest days in each

configuration, and complete trajectory data are available from OpenSky.

The OpenSky ADS-B dataset includes both visual flight rules (VFR) and instrument flight rules (IFR) traffic. Consistent with FAA UAM ConOps 2.0, early-stage AAM operations are expected to be conducted under visual flight rules, with pilots maintaining self-separation from other general aviation aircraft. In this study, we therefore use historical IFR trajectories—such as arrivals, departures, and transition routes—to identify persistent, procedure-constrained airspace. IFR traffic is highly structured and imposes the greatest workload on air traffic controllers; consequently, airspace associated with IFR operations is treated as unavailable when constructing AAM flight routes in order to minimize interference with conventional commercial traffic. Additionally, the analysis is limited to traffic at or below 3,000 feet MSL, reflecting the assumption that early AAM operations will predominantly occur within this altitude range.

To filter most VFR traffic from the dataset, we eliminated all call signs beginning with “N.” Therefore, some business jets on IFR flight plans are excluded, and some flight school aircraft operating VFR using assigned call signs are included. We also eliminated all Coast Guard aircraft, as there is a great deal of VFR helicopter traffic in the vicinity of St. Pete-Clearwater International Airport (PIE). Finally, we eliminated Civil Air Patrol flights, most of which operate VFR.

small UAS pilots operations in controlled airspace. While LAANC uses two-dimensional airspace grids around airports to automatically approve operations in uncongested airspace below 400 ft AGL [23], our framework extends this concept to three dimensions to capture altitude-dependent traffic density. Using filtered trajectory data, we counted the number of flight crossings within each three-dimensional cell (cube) over the two combined study days of March 13 and 18, 2022. Because AAM routes are expected to avoid cubes with heavy conventional flights, the grid resolution was selected to balance two competing objectives: maintaining adequate separation from

Next, we discretized the study-area airspace into a three-dimensional grid. This approach is similar to the FAA’s Low Altitude Authorization and Notification Capability (LAANC), which supports automated evaluation of airspace authorization requests from

conventional aircraft flows while allowing sufficiently flexible AAM routing.

Figure 1 TPA daily operations comparison, ASPM and OpenSky, Fiscal Year 2022

In the absence of established regulatory thresholds, we used existing, charted VFR flyways to inform the selection of both cubical size and the threshold for flight trajectory density. As shown in Figure 2A, the Tampa VFR Terminal Area Chart depicts a designated VFR flyway—identified by double-sided magenta arrows oriented east-west—commonly referred to as the "Bridge Transition." Tampa TRACON routinely uses this corridor to allow VFR aircraft to transit directly through the middle of the Class B airspace and over TPA. Accordingly, the airspace analysis framework was designed to preserve this corridor while restricting AAM operations in airspace heavily utilized by approach and departure flows to the parallel runways at TPA. The selected cubical dimensions and threshold of 40 daily trajectory crossings successfully achieved these objectives. As illustrated in the 2,500-3,000 ft altitude slice (Figure 2B), the VFR flyway remains clear, whereas approach and departure paths associated with the parallel runways—as well as approach corridors to St. Pete-Clearwater International Airport (PIE) and SRQ (Sarasota-Bradenton International Airport)—are appropriately restricted. As AAM concepts of operations evolve and traffic density increases, future research can further refine the optimal cubical size and associated traffic density threshold.

We did not perform rigorous optimization or sensitivity analyses for these parameters, as the time and budget constraints of this study did not permit extensive

simulation. The primary objective of this research is to address the extended p-Hub problem for AAM network design; further refinement and systematic evaluation of the airspace analysis methodology are therefore left to future work.

Following the procedures described in the research approach, we identified restricted airspace cubes at multiple altitude layers within the study airspace (Figure 3A). Once the airspace to be avoided was delineated, routes between vertiports were generated using a visibility graph technique, as described by Tang et al. [24]. Figure 3B illustrates an example of such a route between two notional vertiports. In this case, the shortest path leverages the existing VFR corridor over TPA to traverse from the west to the east side of the airport while avoiding congested airspace. When either the origin or destination vertiport is located within congested airspace, the routing procedure is adjusted such that the path first follows the shortest feasible trajectory to exit the congested airspace, after which the visibility graph method is applied to complete the route to the destination. It should be noted that the precise AAM corridor in the vicinity of airports warrants further investigation to ensure safe operations [25]. In this study, using the approach as described, routes were generated for all vertiport pairs while avoiding identified congested airspace.

The result of the visibility graph technique increases time and distance for 48% (or 1,126,990 flight routes) of AAM flights (Figure 4). Most of the flying time would increase by 0.54 miles and 1.72 minutes.

Therefore, our airspace analysis shows that airspace obstacles have a significant effect on AAM operational costs.

A. VFR route flyer around TPA

B. Restricted Airspace at 2,500 to 3,000 ft

Figure 2 Class B airspace around Tampa International Airport (TPA) and a VFR flyway crossing the airspace

A. Restricted airspace at different altitudes

B. Air links between vertiport pairs

Figure 3 Illustration of airspace analysis for obtaining the flying distance between vertiport pairs

Figure 4 AAM flying distance and time increase when considering airspace obstacles

3.3 Extended Multiple Allocation P-Hub Median Problem (E-MApHMP)

This study proposes an E-MApHMP optimization model to determine the best vertiport locations in the study area, and estimates the trips shifted to multimodal AAM. Wu and Zhang [10] applied extended p-Hub median problem to find optimal vertiport locations and estimate shifted demand. They worked on individual trip data, so their p-Hub median problem is a single allocation problem. However, this study used the TAZ-level demand from regional travel demand modeling. So, it is a multiple-allocation p-Hub median problem because a TAZ could be linked to multiple vertiports. In this model, we assume that for trips between TAZs, all demand shifts to AAM when the generalized cost of AAM travel is lower than that of ground transportation. This assumption is necessitated by data limitations in the Florida statewide travel demand model, which provides only median household income for each TAZ rather than a full income distribution. As a result, the demand component in E-MApHMP formulation is treated deterministically. Future research will relax this assumption by incorporating income heterogeneity within TAZs, allowing demand to be segmented across traveler groups with different income levels. 0 shows the notations for mathematical formulation.

Intrinsically, an AAM trip is an intermodal trip, starting from the origin TAZ, accessing the first vertiport via available ground transportation modes (transit, for-hire, or automobile), flying to the second vertiport via eVTOL, and egressing from the second vertiport to the destination through available modes (transit or for-hire). The generalized cost of a multimodal AAM trip consists of the costs of these different phases. Because different ground access and egress modes are available within the region, only the combinations that minimize the total generalized cost of a multimodal AAM trip are considered in the optimization model. Accordingly, all demand between a given pair of TAZs is assumed to use the same optimal access and egress mode combination.

The generalized cost of a multimodal AAM trip is expressed as:

$$GC_{ij}^{mn} = GC_{im}^{acc} + GC_{mn}^{air} + GC_{nj}^{egr} \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$GC_{im}^{acc} = \min_{g \in G} GC_{im}^g \quad (2)$$

$$GC_{mn}^{air} = c^{mn} + \gamma_i t^{mn} \quad (3)$$

$$GC_{nj}^{egr} = \min_{g \in G_{egr}} GC_{nj}^g \quad (4)$$

TABLE II Mathematic Notations

Sets	Definition
N	Set of TAZs (1, ..., n)
G	Set of ground transportation modes (s for transit, l for for-hire, p for automobile)
G_{egr}	Set of ground transportation modes for egress part of multimodal AAM (No automobile)
Indices	Definition
$i, j \in N$	Represent TAZs
$m, n \in N$	Represent potential vertiport locations.
$g \in G$	Represent different ground transportation modes.
v	Represents vertiport location.
Parameters	Definition
V	Number of vertiports
d_{ij}^g	Total traffic from i to j via transportation mode g
M_v	Total number of AAM trips that can access vertiport v (as a Big M)
N_v	Total number of AAM trips that can egress from vertiport v (as a Big M)
γ_i	Value of time for trips starting from TAZ i
t_{ij}^g	Travel time from i to j with mode g . $i, j \in N, g \in G$
t^{mn}	AAM Travel time from vertiport m to n
c^{mn}	AAM Travel cost from vertiport m to n
c_{ij}^g	Ground Transportation cost from i to j by mode g
GC_{ij}^{mn}	Generalized cost of multimodal AAM tip from i to j using vertiports m to n
$GC_{ij}^g = c_{ij}^g + \gamma_i t_{ij}^g$	Generalized cost of ground transportation mode g from i to j
GC_{im}^{acc}	Minimum generalized cost for access from i to vertiport m across all available transportation modes
GC_{nj}^{egr}	Minimum generalized cost for egress from vertiport n to j across for-hire and transit
GC_{mn}^{air}	Generalized cost of flight via AAM from vertiport m to n
p_{mn}	The penalty cost if air travel time between vertiport m and n is less than 10 minutes (0 otherwise)
Decision variables	Definition
z_v	1 if v is selected as vertiport, 0 otherwise.
y_{ij}^{mn}	1 if ground transportation from i to j via mode g shifts to AAM and uses vertiports m to n , 0 otherwise
z_{mn}	1 if m and n are selected as vertiport, 0 otherwise.

The objective function of E-MAPhMP minimizes the total generalized travel cost of all trips in the study region after AAM is introduced, which is equivalent to maximizing the reduced generalized cost of shifted trips, i.e., the trips shifting from various ground transportation modes to multimodal AAM. In addition, penalty is introduced if flight time of eVTOLs is shorter than 10 minutes (this threshold will be explored for multiple values in the sensitivity analysis). This penalty is used to avoid short eVTOL flights that are not operational feasible. The mathematic formulation of the optimization model is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Max} \quad & \sum_i \sum_j \sum_m \sum_n (GC_{ij}^g - GC_{ij}^{mn}) d_{ij}^g y_{ij}^{mn} \\ & - \sum_{m \in N} \sum_{n \in N} p_{mn} z_{mn} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{v \in N} z_v = V \quad (6)$$

$$z_{mn} \geq z_m + z_n - 1, \quad \forall m, n \in N \quad (7)$$

$$z_{mn} \leq z_m, \quad \forall m, n \in N \quad (8)$$

$$z_{mn} \leq z_n, \quad \forall m, n \in N \quad (9)$$

$$\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{n \neq v} \sum_g y_{ij}^{vn} \leq M_v z_v, \quad \forall v \in N \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{m \neq v} \sum_g y_{ij}^{mv} \leq N_v z_v, \quad \forall v \in N \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_m \sum_{n \neq m} y_{ij}^{mn} \leq 1, \quad \forall i, j \in N \quad (12)$$

$$y_{ij}^{mn}, z_{mn}, z_m \in \{1,0\}, \quad \forall i, j, m, n \in N \quad (13)$$

Constraint 6 ensures that the total number of vertipoints is limited to V . In the baseline scenario, 30 vertipoints will be located, and in the sensitivity analysis, multiple values will be tested to explore the impact of number of vertipoints on the AAM demand. Constraints 7 to 9 enforce that if both m and n are selected as vertipoints, z_{mn} will take the value of 1, otherwise 0. Constraints 10 and 11 ensure that AAM multimodal trips can access or egress from the site v only if a vertipoint exists at the location v . Constraint 12 ensures that the AAM trip from i to j is only assigned to one multimodal AAM route when shifting to AAM. Finally, constraint 10 specifies the domains of variables.

3.4 Three-Part Chromosome Genetic Algorithm (3Part-GA) with Local Search Strategies

If there is no mode selection constraint, E-MAPhMP generalizes the p -median problem, which is an NP-hard problem. Therefore, it would be heavily time-consuming to solve a large-scale E-MAPhMP. Since the E-MAPhMP includes 2D data of the OD matrix and the AAM multimodal route, we developed a three-part chromosome representation (3Part-GA) (Figure 5). Vertipoint vector V (length $n = \text{number TAZs}$) is the first part, and V_i represents TAZ i . V_i takes the value of 1 if it is selected as vertipoints and 0 otherwise. The second part, the matrix S (size of $n \times n$) is a 2D binary matrix representing OD trips, and S_{ij} will take the value of 1 if it shifts from ground transportation to AAM and 0 otherwise. The third part of the chromosome is the access/egress matrix AE (size of $n \times n$). If S_{ij} is 1, AE_{ij} takes a pair of m and n vertipoint for access and egress, otherwise AE_{ij} has no value. Once the V and S are formed, matrix AE will be randomly generated based on the available vertipoints for shifted ODs in S . It should be noted that if a trip from i to j has no possible access/egress (within a 30-

minute limit), given a specific set of vertipoints, S_{ij} never shifts to AAM and takes the value of 1.

The remainder of this section explains each operation within the proposed GA.

3.4.1 Crossover

Multiple 2D crossovers were tested to figure out the one with the best performance. Among one-point, two-point, column-uniform, row-uniform, and column-row uniform crossovers, the column-row uniform crossover was the most suitable for the algorithm. Algorithm 1 demonstrates the procedure of performing a column-row uniform crossover to generate a single offspring. In column-row uniform crossover, the offspring will take the gene V_i from the first or second parent based on a uniform probability. Algorithm 1:2-3 generates a random probability vector to decide from which parent V_i will be inherited. If V_i comes from parent 1, column and row i of the matrix S and AE will also come from parent 1 (Algorithm 1:5-9). Figure 6 Shows an example of column-row uniform crossover with $n = 6$ and 2 selected vertipoints on the first and second part of chromosomes. In this example, the points that have been chosen uniformly is shown with black arrows. First, offspring 1 will be made of columns and rows 2, 4, and 6 from parent 1, then the remaining genes of the matrix S will come from columns&rows 1, 3, and 5 of parent 2. On the contrary with offspring 1, firstly, columns and rows 1, 3, and 5 of parent 2 enumerate offspring 2, and then the remaining genes come from parent 1. After finalizing this step, there might be some inconsistency in the number of selected vertipoints and in the Access/egress link (because the vertipoints set might change during offspring processing). We randomly fix the inconsistency in the number of vertipoints by either removing some of the extra vertipoints or adding extra vertipoints to the vector V to match the number of vertipoints (Algorithm 1:10-11). In the next step, Algorithm 1:12-16 constructs the possible vertipoints for each TAZ given selected vertipoints in the solution (B^V) and finds ODs that have a non-vertipoint for access/egress. For AE , those genes that have access/egress links to non-available vertipoints, a vertipoint will be selected randomly (Algorithm 1:19-21). If there is no possible vertipoint in the gene vertipoint pools, that OD will be shifted back to ground transportation (Algorithm 1:17).

Figure 5 GA 3-part chromosome representation

Figure 6 Column-row uniform crossovers example (only representing first and second chromosome part)

Algorithm 1 Crossover operation in 3-part Chromosome GA

```
1:  $x_1, x_2 \leftarrow \text{parents}$ 
2:  $\text{rand} = (r_1, \dots, r_n)^\top$ ,  $r_i \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} U(0, 1)$ ,  $i = 1, \dots, |TAZs|$ 
3:  $\text{mask} = \mathbb{I}(\text{rand} < \text{crossover gene probability})$ 
4:  $\text{Child}^1 = \text{mask} \odot x_1 + (1 - \text{mask}) \odot x_2$ 
5: for  $k \in \{2, 3\}$  do
6:    $\text{Child}^{(k)} \leftarrow x_2^{(k)}$ 
7:    $\text{Child}^{(k)}(\text{mask} = 1, :) \leftarrow x_1^{(k)}(\text{mask} = 1, :)$ 
8:    $\text{Child}^{(k)}(:, \text{mask} = 1) \leftarrow x_1^{(k)}(:, \text{mask} = 1)$ 
9: end for
10:  $V = \{v \in \{1, \dots, n\} \mid \text{Child}^1 = 1\}$ 
11:  $|V| \neq 30$ : then add/remove vertiport based on probability P
12:  $B = (B_1, \dots, B_n)$ ,  $B_i$  allowable access/egress vertiports for node
13:  $B^V = \{B_i \in B \mid B_i \subseteq V\}$ 
14:  $\text{repair} = \{(i, j) \mid m : \text{child}_{ij}^3[0] \notin V \text{ or } n : \text{child}_{ij}^3[1] \notin V\}$ 
15: for  $(i, j) \in \text{repair}$  do
16:   if  $|B_i^V| = 0$  or  $|B_j^V| = 0$ :
17:      $\text{child}_{ij}^2 = 0$ ,  $\text{child}_{ij}^3 = \text{nan}$ 
18:     continue
19:   sample  $v_1 \in B_i^V$ 
20:   sample  $v_2 \in B_j^V$ 
21:    $\text{child}_{ij}^3 \leftarrow (v_1, v_2)$ 
22: end for
23: return child
```

3.4.2 Fitness evaluation

In GA, if parents are selected based on objective values, the population diversity might decline over time. Early low diversity results in early termination and not in-depth search of solution space. To maintain diversity, a fitness value is calculated for each chromosome.

The difference between two chromosome c_1 and c_2 is calculated based on the normalized Hamming distance [26], formulated as equation 11, where n is the number of genes. Function f equals 1 if gene i is different between the two chromosomes and 0 otherwise. δ could get a value between zero and one. If δ equals 0, it indicates that two chromosomes are identical; a value of 1 indicates that two are entirely different.

$$\delta(c_1, c_2) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(c_1[i] \neq c_2[i]) \quad (11)$$

To calculate the diversity, the algorithm first sorts of chromosomes based on the objective value. Then, the diversity contribution of each chromosome will be the

average of two closest neighbors in the sorted population (shown as $\Delta\delta_c$). Finally, the fitness of the chromosome c is calculated using Equation 12.

$$F_c = \text{objective}_c \times \text{diversity factor}^{\Delta\delta_c} \quad (12)$$

Algorithm 2 demonstrates the pseudo-code for the fitness evaluation. It should be noted that chromosomes 1, 2, $|Pop| - 2$, and $|Pop| - 1$ have fewer neighbors. Algorithm 2:3 upholds this rule when finding the four neighbors in the sorted population.

Algorithm 2 Fitness Evaluation

```
1: define for any chromosome  $a$  and  $b$ :  $\delta(a, b) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{1}_{\{a_i \neq b_i\}}$ 
2: define  $df$  as diversity factor
3: for  $c \leftarrow 0$  to  $|Pop| - 1$  do:
4:    $\text{low} = \max(0, c - 2)$ ,  $\text{high} = \min(|Pop| - 1, c + 2)$ 
5:    $\Delta\delta_c = \frac{1}{\text{high} - \text{low}} \sum_{\substack{r=\text{low} \\ r \neq c}}^{\text{high}} \delta(\text{Pop}_c, \text{Pop}_r)$ 
6:    $F_c = \text{Obj}_c \times df^{\Delta\delta_c}$ 
7: end for
8: return F
```

3.4.3 Parent Selection

Before a crossover operation, two parents must be selected to create new offspring. We evaluated the performance of four standard parent selection methods: tournament, elite, top rank, and random selection. Tournament selection with two groups of k chromosomes performs better during the early stages of the proposed GA. In tournament selection, two groups of k members are randomly selected as candidates. The member with the highest fitness value in each group is then chosen as a parent.

3.4.4 Mutation

When the whole crossover operation is finished, we randomly select a non-vertiport and vertiport gene from V and change them. The mutation is mainly performed on the first and second parts of the chromosome, and the mutation only repairs the third part because the vertiport set and shifted ODs are changed. When two genes of V (hub' and $nonHub'$) have been switched (Algorithm 3:3), the same column and row in the matrix S will be redefined. Algorithm 3:4-5 redefines the column and row of hub' and $nonHub'$. Repairing AE matrix follows the same process as Algorithm 1, which handles access and egress to non-vertiports (Algorithm 3:9-15). Figure 7 is an example of the implemented mutation operation for a chromosome with $n = 6$ and 2 selected vertiports.

Figure 7 Example of mutation operation for the proposed GA

Algorithm 3 Mutation operation in 3-part Chromosome GA

```

1:  $x$  as chromosome
2:  $hub'$  as current vertiport,  $nonHub'$  as new vertiport
3:  $x_{hub'}^1 = 0, x_{nonHub'}^1 = 1$ 
4:  $x_{hub'}^2 \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_{hub',:}), x_{nonHub'}^2 \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_{:,hub'})$ 
5:  $x_{nonHub'}^3 \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_{nonHub',:}), x_{hub'}^3 \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_{:,nonHub'})$ 
6:  $V = \{v \in \{1, \dots, n\} \mid x^1 = 1\}$ 
7:  $B^V = \{B_i \in B \mid B_i \subseteq V\}$ 
8:  $repair = \{(i, j) \mid m : x_{ij}^3[0] \notin V \text{ or } n : x_{ij}^3[1] \notin V\}$ 
9: for  $(i, j) \in repair$  do
10:   if  $|B_i^V| = 0$  or  $|B_j^V| = 0$  :
11:      $child_{ij}^0 = 0, child_{ij}^1 = nan$ 
12:   continue
13:   sample  $v_1 \in B_i^V$ 
14:   sample  $v_2 \in B_j^V$ 
15:    $child_{ij}^0 \leftarrow (v_1, v_2)$ 
16: end for
17: return  $x$ 

```

3.4.5 Local Search

The local search strategy in the proposed GA comprises two sections. The first section is performed on the matrix S to redefine the ODs shift decision in the row and column with the lowest saved generalized cost. This strategy is applied to created offspring to improve the quality of their objective value. However, the second local search section improves the best-found solution in each GA iteration, and it is focused on the AE matrix. Given a set of vertiports and shifted AAM trips, AAM ODs might have multiple vertiports for access/egress. Our local search will improve the access/egress link to achieve a better saved generalized cost. To clarify the process, in the network shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**Figure 8, trips A- V_2 - V_3 -E and D- V_2 - V_3 -F have V_1 and V_2 for access to the AAM network. While they go through V_2 in the current solution, during the local search, we switch their access link to the V_1 to get a better solution quality.

Figure 8 A small network of AAM access/egress links

3.4.6 Initial Solutions

We assume that trips starting from TAZs with higher VOT have a higher possibility of shifting to AAM mode. Therefore, we implement a greedy initial solution generation and shift all ODs with high VOT (larger than 50 USD) and higher than 30 minutes of ground travel time. As a result, we start the chromosome population with a better solution quality than purely random generation.

3.4.7 Adaptive Strategies

Two adaptive strategies have been implemented for the proposed GA to improve the algorithm further. Firstly, instead of purely randomly making the shifting decision in the matrix S , we adjust the probability of S_{ij} shifting to AAM based on the following conditions:

1. Start all ODs shift probability with θ_{ij}
2. If an OD has a negative generalized cost, decrease θ_{ij} by e (after multiple value tests, e has been set to 0.01)
3. If an OD has a positive generalized cost, increase θ_{ij} by e
4. If an OD has a positive saved generalized cost, and after a change in the chromosome, it takes a better saved generalized cost, increase θ_{ij} by e_{max} (after multiple value tests, e_{max} has been set to 0.02)

The second improvement is related to the probability of selecting a TAZ as a vertiport. In the whole algorithm, whenever a TAZ has been selected as a vertiport, its contribution to the saved generalized cost of the transportation network will be recorded. This value will be updated during the GA algorithm when the vertiport contribution increases. Equations 12 and 13 below were used to calculate the probability of a TAZ being selected. The calculated probability values were used as input parameters for generating solutions in iterations of the GA algorithm. Equation 12 defines the Contribution of a potential vertiport, which equals the maximum possible saved generalized cost if the TAZ v was selected to locate a vertiport. Equation 13 calculates the p_v , i.e., the probability of a TAZ v being selected to locate a vertiport, which equals the ratio of contribution v divided by the summation of all contributions.

$$\text{contribution}_v = \sum_i \sum_j \sum_m \text{savedCost}_{ij}^{mv} + \sum_i \sum_j \sum_n \text{savedCost}_{ij}^{pn} \quad (12)$$

$$p_v = \frac{\text{contribution}_v}{\sum_v \text{contribution}_v} \quad (13)$$

Algorithm 4 in **Error! Reference source not found.** is the pseudo-code of the proposed 3-part chromosome GA that shows the algorithm's specific steps and overall process.

Algorithm 4, with its supporting algorithms, contains four parameters that affect the time complexity: V as the number of candidate locations (TAZs in our study), \bar{k} as the number of vertiports that passengers in one TAZ can access within a given time threshold (e.g., 30 minutes), G as the number of iterations, and $K = |Pop|$ as the population size. One GA generation runs in $O(K n^2 \bar{k}^2)$ time and uses $O(n^2 \bar{k}^2)$ memory for the sparse cost tensor; therefore, the total runtime is $O(GK n^2 \bar{k}^2)$. Since $\bar{k} \ll V$, time complexity depends on \bar{k} rather than the full candidate set.

3.4.8 3Part-GA Parameters

TABLE III includes all hyperparameters used in the proposed GA that yielded the most efficient results in terms of both computational efficiency and solution quality. The following values are selected based on the results of 10 GA tests with predefined seeds (1, 13, 113, 1311, 3123, 11027, 11241, 76351, 87621, 92376) on

multiple values for each hyperparameter. We perform the GA for any seed with various values for each parameter independently, and values in TABLE III represents those that resulted in the least gap between the GA and the MIP solver. For the tournament selection size and diversity factor for fitness evaluation, we evaluate their interaction on the gap percentage. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the change in the GA gap, given the tournament selection size and diversity factors. Each line represents a diversity factor; tournament selection size 5 and diversity factor 1.2 yields the best gap.

Algorithm 4 Proposed 3-part Chromosome Genetic Algorithm

```

1:  $n \leftarrow |TAZs|, q \leftarrow PopSize$ 
2: Initiate vertiports contribution:  $P_v \quad \forall TAZs$ 
3: Initiate ODs shift probability:  $\theta \in [0, 1]^{n \times n}$ 
4: Initial generalized cost of ODs:  $GC^{AAM} = 0_{n \times n}$ 
5:  $Pop \leftarrow$  greedy Initialize( $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_q | x_c = (x_c^1, x_c^2, x_c^3)$ )

 $x_c^1 \in \{0, 1\}^n, \quad x_c^2 \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}, \quad x_c^3 \in \{v_1, v_2\}^{n \times n}$ 

6:  $Obj_c =$  equation 5,  $\forall x_c \in Pop$ 
7:  $F \leftarrow$  evaluate( $\forall x_c \in Pop$ )
8: update  $P$  and  $\theta$ 
9:  $x^* = \arg \max_{c \in Pop} Obj_c$ 
10: while No improvement in max iterations do
11:    $T_1, T_2 \sim Pop, |T_1, T_2| = 5$ 
12:    $x_1 = \arg \max_{c \in T_1} F_c, \quad x_2 = \arg \max_{c \in T_2} F_c$ 
13:   Algorithm 1:  $x_{child1}, x_{child2} \leftarrow$  crossover( $x_1, x_2$ )
14:   for offspring do
15:     Manage child inconsistency
16:      $hub' \sim x_{child}^1 (\{i | x_{child}^1 = 1\}$  with probability  $P$ )
17:      $nonHub' \sim x_{child}^1 (\{i | x_{child}^1 = 0\}$  with probability  $P$ )
18:     if  $\mathcal{U}(0, 1) <$  mutation probability
19:       Algorithm 2:  $x_{child} \leftarrow$  Mutation( $x_{child}, hub', nonHub'$ )
20:      $Obj_{child} =$  equation 5
21:     Update  $P_{nonHub'}$ 
22:      $i, j \leftarrow$  worst row and column of  $GC_{child}^{AAM}$ 
23:     if  $\mathcal{U}(0, 1) <$  local search probability
24:       localSearch( $x_{child}, i, j$ )
25:     Update  $\theta$  and  $GC$ 
26:   end for
27:    $Pop \leftarrow Pop \cup \{x_{child1}, x_{child2}\}$ 
28:   sort  $Pop$  based on  $Obj$ 
29:   while  $|Pop| >$  max population do
30:      $Pop \leftarrow Pop \setminus \{\text{worst}(Pop)\}$ 
31:   end while
32:   Update  $F$ 
33:    $x^* = Pop[0]$ 
34:    $x^* \leftarrow$  local Neighborhood Search( $x^*$ )
35: end while
36: output Best Solution  $x^*$ 

```

Figure 9 Interaction of tournament selection size and diversity factor on the gap

TABLE III Hyperparameter values for the proposed GA

Hyperparameters	Value
Initial Population size	50
Max Population Size	100
Termination condition	500 iterations with no improvement
Size for tournament selection (k)	5
Mutation probability	0.4
Crossover gene probability	0.5
Probability for Local search	0.8
Number of Neighborhoods	2
Diversity Factor for Fitness Calculation	1.2
e and e_{max}	0.01 and 0.02

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 GA Results and Base Scenario

The base scenario that is used for comparing GA with the off-shelf solver was for 30 vertiports, 30 minutes access/egress limit, and the AAM pricing scheme presented in TABLE I. To compare GA results with Gurobi's, we randomly generated multiple problem sizes ranging from 10 to 1521 TAZs (main problem). Instances are named in the *inst_TAZ_candidate* format that shows the number of TAZs and candidates. Because the MIP solver could not solve all the instances in a timely manner, problems are grouped into small-medium and large instances. For any instance, Gurobi and the metaheuristic algorithms run with initial seeds of 1, 13, 113, 1311, 3123, 11027, 11241, 76351, 87621, and 92376 on a machine with 13th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-13700, 2100 MHz, 16 Core(s), 24 Logical Processor(s), windows 10, and 32 GB RAM. For small-medium instances, Gurobi stops

if gap is under 5%. However, instances of this size could not reach under 5%, and Gurobi stops after 600 minutes. In addition, Gurobi is allowed to use the hard drive if the memory runs out of capacity.

The initial seed and termination condition are the only two set parameters for Gurobi. TBR+ instances are region-scale and large, and exhaustive tuning across sizes would be computationally prohibitive and not reflective of a practitioner baseline. To show the effect of tuning, we tuned the Gurobi for a sample of 100 TAZs and 30 vertiports. We tuned Gurobi for MIP focus strategies, MIP gap, Intensity of Heuristic, strength of primal cutting plans, number of threads (2, 4, 8, 16, 24), and seeds (1, 13, 113, 1311, 3123, 11027, 11241, 76351, 87621, and 92376). When MIP focus is on default, MIP gap of 5 percent, intensity of Heuristic of 0.2, cutting plans of conservative, 32 threads, Gurobi reports the found solution reported in TABLE IV for the *inst_100_30*. Other Gurobi settings either increased the solution time or worsened the final found incumbent. This means that Gurobi gives the best solution without tuning. Therefore, the sample Gurobi tuning shows that our conclusions are robust to reasonable parameter choices and that extensive tuning does not close the gap on large instances within the same wall-time/memory budgets.

In addition to Gurobi and 3Part-GA, we compare the performance results with other metaheuristic algorithms. 2D-GA is a simplified version of 3Part-GA in which matrix AE does not exist, and access or egress link for any OD should be determined by running a shortest path on each chromosome. Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) and Simulated Annealing (SA) are based on algorithms proposed by Brimberg et al. [20] and Demir et al. [18], respectively. We ran 3Part-GA without the local search and without the GA wrapper (turning the algorithm into a simple local search) to compare the effect of local search and the necessity of the GA wrapper.

TABLE IV represents the comparison result for small to medium instances. For any algorithm, the table reports the average runtime in minutes. Gurobi results display the average best objective (incumbent), while meta-heuristic algorithms show the average gap from the Gurobi objective. For instance, the meta-heuristic gaps are calculated seed by seed, and the final gap in the table shows the average gap over all seeds. For TAZ size under 50, Gurobi outperforms all meta-heuristics

in runtime, and the following algorithm is 3Part-GA. When TAZ size increases over 50, the Gurobi solutions are still better than meta-heuristic algorithms in terms of found objective, but they found an acceptable solution in lower runtime. 3Part-GA found the best solution among the meta-heuristic algorithms, both in terms of gap and runtime. The best result comes from the 3Par-GA for inst_100_10 and inst_100_20 with a gap of 0.02% and a runtime of almost 8.5 minutes.

TABLE IV Comparison of proposed GA vs. Gurobi solver vs. selected metahurestics: small to medium instances

Instance	Gurobi		2D-GA		VNS		SA		3Part-GA without local search		No GA wrapper local search		3Part-GA	
	Obj	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time
inst_10_5	2.9	0.1	0.00%	1.98	0.00%	2.59	0.00%	2.84	0.00%	1.79	0.00%	2.72	0.00%	1.47
inst_50_5	23.1	1.55	0.00%	19.67	0.00%	8.51	0.00%	14.69	0.00%	4.91	0.00%	4.80	0.00%	2.71
inst_50_10	41.1	1.23	0.00%	18.25	0.00%	12.27	0.00%	9.34	0.00%	5.49	0.00%	5.43	0.00%	1.95
inst_50_20	91.3	1.15	0.00%	10.74	0.00%	20.03	-0.20%	4.76	0.00%	7.42	0.00%	7.99	0.00%	2.66
inst_50_30	141.7	1.09	0.00%	16.05	0.00%	12.30	-0.50%	7.26	0.00%	13.11	0.00%	10.49	0.00%	2.26
inst_100_5	181.8	36.78	-1.19%	32.25	-0.39%	69.74	-1.07%	13.59	-1.08%	13.36	-2.18%	13.00	-0.42%	6.83
inst_100_10	236.1	30.22	-2.67%	70.64	-2.05%	76.91	-2.90%	17.46	-2.64%	14.56	-2.90%	13.40	-0.02%	8.48
inst_100_20	2,319.2	27.35	-1.51%	51.96	-6.80%	58.50	-6.93%	13.86	-1.45%	15.44	-2.45%	12.50	-0.02%	8.84
inst_100_30	5,296.6	25.47	-2.82%	110.68	-4.41%	99.90	-5.11%	14.39	-2.69%	14.06	-3.73%	11.81	-0.28%	10.12
inst_500_5	2,099.4	593.93	-10.81%	168.14	-14.44%	97.04	-16.21%	29.37	-9.92%	26.81	-13.34%	20.14	-0.22%	27.13
inst_500_10	9,784.5	534.09	-8.22%	214.08	-14.46%	116.14	-16.66%	27.00	-8.06%	29.00	-13.31%	25.24	-0.36%	29.1
inst_500_20	5,466.0	527.56	-9.18%	172.80	-12.22%	99.58	-18.84%	25.05	-8.56%	23.02	-14.07%	24.08	-0.31%	26.87
inst_500_30	9,448.8	479.23	-8.10%	130.56	-12.35%	83.19	-18.95%	24.97	-7.64%	21.88	-12.99%	20.01	-0.50%	20.68

Time Unit: minutes

In TABLE I, Gurobi is limited to 600 minutes for all instances except for the main problem size (inst_1521_30). As shown, except for the main problem size, Gurobi found bad solutions, with large negative values, indicating that many vertiports are close to each other. When meta-heuristic gaps are under 100%, it means the algorithm has found a solution with a negative objective value. The only algorithm that could achieve a positive objective value was 3Part-GA (the best result is for inst_100_30 with 102.23% gap).

Analyzing inst_1521_30 gives a clearer perspective on the algorithms' performance. Gurobi found a solution with an objective of 31,992.7, which required 6,523 minutes to reach a 2.33% gap. 3Part-GA solution outperformed Gurobi by a gap of 0.42% over 33.7

minutes. The next algorithm with the lowest gap is 3Part-GA without local search, and No GA wrapper local search algorithm achieved one of the highest gaps of -22.30%. Local search and the GA wrapper significantly improve the solution quality of 3-part chromosome algorithms. The 3Part-GA solution for the main problem size resulted in 7,058 trips estimated to shift to AAM, representing 0.05% of total travel demand that could shift to AAM (but with a lower generalized cost than using AAM). If it is assumed that daily AAM operation is 18 hours and the capacity of each flight equals 4, there should be 98 AAM flights per hour to accommodate 7,058 trips. This level of flight for the early stage of AAM is considered acceptable, as the AAM flight links in our study are designed to avoid airspace obstacles and rely minimally on ATCs.

TABLE VI Comparison of proposed GA vs. Gurobi solver vs. selected metaheuristics: large instances

Instance	Gurobi	2D-GA		VNS		SA		3Part-GA without local search		No GA wrapper local search		3Part-GA	
	Obj	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time	Gap%	Time
inst_1000_5	-419,947.1	91.60%	127.40	91.00%	223.77	88.21%	34.18	96.55%	52.06	88.82%	51.00	101.29%	32.47
inst_1000_10	-1,500,468.3	92.88%	158.16	91.58%	233.68	64.24%	48.48	95.76%	68.47	89.00%	62.17	100.96%	37.08
inst_1000_20	-2,021,838.2	93.69%	131.93	87.02%	234.34	85.85%	46.32	96.23%	68.01	88.82%	62.76	100.93%	39.01
inst_1000_30	-1,109,124.4	93.08%	127.61	89.48%	251.84	78.15%	43.00	95.50%	75.57	94.91%	70.50	102.23%	22.38
inst_1521_5	-601,894.0	92.03%	121.08	94.53%	272.84	61.87%	41.95	95.31%	75.69	87.89%	67.46	101.20%	33.29
inst_1521_10	-5,039,299.7	94.03%	117.65	93.25%	281.93	82.80%	49.54	97.95%	85.23	90.96%	64.64	100.35%	31.74
inst_1521_20	-2,332,397.7	95.77%	155.63	94.08%	305.64	70.31%	44.81	98.34%	81.14	89.16%	67.44	101.28%	26.06
inst_1521_30*	31,992.7	-17.46%	115.83	-19.07%	305.92	-36.34%	58.17	-7.30%	71.69	-22.30%	60.69	0.42%	33.7

Time Unit: minutes

4.2 Sensitivity Analysis

To further evaluate the impact of AAM in the study area and the effects of the assumed parameters, we designed a sensitivity analysis to examine changes in AAM demand. FLSWM contains 2045-year scenarios, enabling our sensitivity analysis to explore future AAM demand. The design sensitivity analysis is a factorial design based on a Type-II ANOVA. The sensitivity analysis is from the perspective of the AAM operator. Therefore, we assumed a set of parameters that the AAM operator could control. 0 list the independent parameters for the Type-II ANOVA and their range of values. In this paper, the dependent variables for Type-II ANOVA are demand, share of low-income groups of AAM (annual income lower than 40,000 USD), and access/egress travel miles. To fully complete this factorial design, 3Part-GA runs 900 times, given the input independent parameter range.

To estimate how each factor and each pairwise interaction affects the response parameter, we have:

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_1^5 \beta_k X_k + \sum_{k<l}^5 \beta_{kl} X_k X_l + \varepsilon$$

Where $X_k \in \{-1, +1\}$ is the coded version of factor k , calculated by the following equation.

$$X_k = -1 + 2 \frac{F - F_{low}}{F_{high} - F_{low}}$$

This equation maps values to two units of coded space, [-1, 1]. It also centers the design, so interactions are orthogonal in a balanced design. We run an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) with heteroskedasticity (heterogeneity of variance) -robust SEs (HC3) and 95% CIs. OLS estimates the coefficients, and HC3 protects standard errors against heteroskedasticity and mild imbalance/unequal replicates. Type-II ANOVA tests the main effect of a factor after adjusting for all other main effects and tests each two-way interaction after adjusting for the two corresponding main effects. That aligns with factorial-design logic and effect hierarchy (mains first, then interactions). Type I and III are not going to be a good fit here. Type-I (“sequential”) depends on term order -undesirable (our estimations led to low R^2). Type-III conditions on everything, which can be unstable or misleading in effects-coded, unbalanced designs (our estimation led to a model with a high R^2 and meaningless coefficient values). Type-II tells how much variation a factor/interaction explains beyond others.

TABLE VII Parameters and their range for factorial design

Parameter	Name in model estimation	Range of Values				
Number of Vertiports	Vertiports	30	40	50	60	70
Base Air Price (\$)	Base Air	10	20	30	35	40
Air Price per mile (\$ per mile)	Air Per Mile	1.5	2	2.5	3	
Vertiport Access Parking Price (\$)	Parking	0	5	10		
Vertiport processing time (minutes)	Processing	5	10	15		

The estimated OLS regression for demand has an adjusted R-squared of 0.334 over 900 observations (TABLE I). Note that the R-squared value is not considerable, but acceptable and expected, given that the response variable is a behavioral demand value for AAM. Processing time at vertiports has the most significant effect on ($|z| \approx 16$) on demand. This implies that shorter processing time strongly increases demand, as the estimated coefficient is negative. From the Type-II ANOVA estimated model, it can be inferred that processing time accounts for almost 30% of the variation in the response variable, as the partial R^2 is 0.298.

An advantage of Type II ANOVA is that it shows the per-unit impact of each factor on AAM demand.

TABLE IX presents the coefficients' effects, delta low to high (change in demand from the lowest parameter value to the highest), and effect per unit. Processing time was the most significant factor affecting demand, and a 1-minute increase in processing time reduces demand by 300. While vertiports are the only positive effect, their per-unit effect is small, meaning that an increasing number of vertiports could, by itself, not result in a significant increase in demand, and other factors are the primary influencers of demand. Among interaction parameters, Base Air \times Air Per Mile ($|z| \approx 4.65$), Air Per Mile \times Parking ($|z| \approx 3.37$), and Base Air \times Parking ($|z| \approx 3.07$) have a significant effect on the response variable.

TABLE VIII OLS Regression estimation and Type-II ANOVA for factorial design

Term	OLS			Type-II ANOVA		
	Coefficient	z	Robust p-value	F Statistic	Partial R-Squared	Robust p-value HC3
Intercept	11747.360	152.582	0.000			
Vertiports	242.297	2.045	0.041	4.669	0.005	0.041
Base Air	-327.745	-2.744	0.006	0.005	0.000	0.006
Air Per Mile	-377.591	-3.046	0.002	0.028	0.000	0.002
Parking	-517.046	-4.829	0.000	10.229	0.011	0.000
Processing	-1503.506	-16.031	0.000	374.931	0.298	0.000
Vertiports \times Base Air	-132.115	-0.701	0.483	0.491	0.001	0.483
Vertiports \times Air Per Mile	-50.322	-0.294	0.769	0.086	0.000	0.769
Vertiports \times Parking	-142.054	-0.971	0.331	0.943	0.001	0.331
Vertiports \times Processing	-8.241	-0.064	0.949	0.004	0.000	0.949
Base Air \times Air Per Mile	909.985	4.655	0.000	21.669	0.024	0.000
Base Air \times Parking	512.498	3.071	0.002	9.428	0.011	0.002
Base Air \times Processing	-28.983	-0.201	0.841	0.040	0.000	0.841
Air Per Mile \times Parking	518.454	3.367	0.001	11.339	0.013	0.001
Air Per Mile \times Processing	150.850	1.120	0.263	1.253	0.001	0.263
Parking \times Processing	79.386	0.672	0.502	0.451	0.001	0.502
Adj. R-squared		0.334			-	
Covariance Type		HC3			-	

TABLE IX Average per-unit impacts of each factor across whole factorial design

Factor	Coefficient Effects	Delta Low to High	Effect per Unit
Vertiports	242.297	484.595	12.115
Base Air	-327.745	-655.490	-21.850
Air Per Mile	-377.591	-755.183	-503.455
Parking	-517.046	-1034.092	-103.409
Processing	-1503.506	-3007.013	-300.701

effect of Air Per Mile depends on the level of Base Air (As shown in the ANOVA table). The steepness of the blue line slopes is -1288 , and the orange line is 532 . Price components are not additive: the demand response to per-mile pricing depends on the base fare. With a low base fare, a higher per-mile cost sharply reduces demand; with a high base fare, the marginal effect of per-mile cost turns positive, indicating that travelers respond to coherent fare bundles rather than either component in isolation.

In air per mile and base air price interaction graph (Figure 10), non-parallel, crossing lines mean the

Figure 10 Air per mile and Base air price interaction graph

The estimated OLS regression model for low-income AAM share converged with an adjusted R-squared of 0.628 (TABLE I). Among all coefficients, air per mile, parking, processing, and the interaction parameter air per mile \times parking had a significant effect on low-income share. Furthermore, parking price had the most dominant impact, accounting for almost 69% of the variance in the response variable. Interestingly, while increasing the price decreases demand (as indicated by the OLS regression of AAM demand), parking price has a positive effect on the low-income share. This

means increasing parking prices and moving vertiports to areas that improve accessibility (improving access/egress trips) for low-income travelers. In addition, TABLE I shows that the per-unit effect of parking price from low to high could be about a 10% increase in the low-income share. On the other hand, a 1 dollar increase in air per mile could decrease the low-income AAM share by 3%. Air per mile and parking have an interaction effect the limit the maximum increase in low-income AAM share to 4% by air per mile low to high effect.

TABLE X OLS Regression estimation and Type-II ANOVA for low-income AAM share

Term	OLS			Type-II ANOVA		
	Coefficient	z	Robust p-value	F Statistic	Partial R-Squared	Robust p-value HC3
Intercept	0.103	82.668	0.000			
Vertiports	0.000	0.000	1.000	0.235	0.000	1.000
Base Air	-0.003	-1.484	0.138	6.584	0.007	0.138
Air Per Mile	-0.022	-14.756	0.000	96.644	0.099	0.000
Parking	0.048	32.423	0.000	1,918.939	0.685	0.000
Processing	-0.006	-3.916	0.000	27.248	0.030	0.000
Vertiports \times Base Air	-0.001	-0.501	0.616	0.251	0.000	0.616
Vertiports \times Air Per Mile	0.000	-0.082	0.934	0.007	0.000	0.934
Vertiports \times Parking	-0.001	-0.443	0.658	0.196	0.000	0.658
Vertiports \times Processing	0.000	-0.009	0.993	0.000	0.000	0.993
Base Air \times Air Per Mile	0.002	0.749	0.454	0.561	0.001	0.454
Base Air \times Parking	0.000	-0.145	0.885	0.021	0.000	0.885
Base Air \times Processing	0.000	-0.108	0.914	0.012	0.000	0.914
Air Per Mile \times Parking	0.033	21.420	0.000	458.821	0.342	0.000
Air Per Mile \times Processing	0.000	-0.079	0.937	0.006	0.000	0.937
Parking \times Processing	0.000	0.012	0.990	0.000	0.000	0.990
Adj. R-squared	0.628			-		
Covariance Type	HC3			-		

TABLE XI Average per-unit impacts of each factor on low-income AAM share

Factor	Coefficient Effects	Delta Low to High	Effect per Unit
Vertiports	0.000	0.000	0.000
Base Air	-0.003	-0.005	0.000
Air Per Mile	-0.022	-0.045	-0.030
Parking	0.048	0.096	0.010
Processing	-0.006	-0.012	-0.001

To further investigate the positive effect of parking prices on AAM low-income share, we reviewed

Figure 11 Change of vertiport location when changing parking price from 0 to 10

vertiport locations where parking prices ranged from 0 to 10, holding the other parameters constant (30 vertiports, flight fare 2 USD/mile, 30 USD base air price, 5 minutes processing time). As is depicted in Figure 11, firstly, with zero parking fees, most vertiports are concentrated in Hillsborough, Pinellas, and Pasco counties. While in 10 USD parking price, vertiports are more scattered in the TBR+. Secondly, when the parking fee is 0, only 2 vertiports are located in low-income TAZs, whereas at 10 USD, 9 vertiports are situated in low-income TAZs. This change of vertiport location may explain the positive effect of parking price on the AAM low-income share.

Another response variable worth investigating was the access/egress travel mile that AAM travelers choose to use AAM multimodal transportation. TABLE XII indicates significant effects for processing time, the interaction between base air price and air per mile, base air with parking, and air per mile with parking price. Among all the significant parameters, processing time at vertiports was the most significant one. These results demonstrate that the number of vertiports is not a significant contributor to decreasing access/egress travel miles (at least for the number of vertiports that we tested in the factorial design). Furthermore, in average per-unit impacts table, the largest access/egress travel mile change is a unit increase of price per mile of AAM flight, which increases the access/egress travel mile by 0.305 miles (0).

TABLE XII Type-II ANOVA estimation for access/egress travel miles

Term	F Statistic	Partial R-Squared	Robust p-value HC3
Vertiports	0.253	0.000	0.059
Base Air	0.031	0.000	0.000
Air Per Mile	0.082	0.000	0.000
Parking	0.238	0.000	0.000
Processing	21.238	0.023	0.183
Vertiports × Base Air	2.913	0.003	0.088
Vertiports × Air Per Mile	3.939	0.004	0.047
Vertiports × Parking	3.037	0.003	0.081
Vertiports × Processing	0.000	0.000	0.996
Base Air × Air Per Mile	15.702	0.017	0.000
Base Air × Parking	17.737	0.020	0.000
Base Air × Processing	0.001	0.000	0.978
Air Per Mile × Parking	16.222	0.018	0.000
Air Per Mile × Processing	0.000	0.000	0.983
Parking × Processing	0.000	0.000	0.999

TABLE XIII Average per-unit impacts of each factor on access/egress travel miles

Factor	Coefficient Effects	Delta Low to High	Effect per Unit
Vertiports	-0.079	-0.158	-0.004
Base Air	0.219	0.438	0.015
Air Per Mile	0.229	0.457	0.305
Parking	0.191	0.382	0.038
Processing	0.055	0.110	0.011

Sensitivity analysis results indicate that the relatively low AAM mode share (0.05%) could increase to over 0.19% (26,575 trips) if certain factors favor AAM adoption, including the number of vertiports, base air price (\$), air price per mile (\$ per mile), vertiport access parking price (\$), and vertiport processing time (minutes). In addition, processing time at vertiport and parking prices were among the most significant factors that could increase AAM demand and, respectively, the AAM share. This calls for prioritizing vertiports in low-parking-cost TAZs or in TAZs with free public parking within a short walking distance. Sensitivity analysis showed that a relatively short processing time (even 3-5 minutes) could result in a significant change in demand margin. Therefore, predictable routing and smooth scheduling should be of high priority for the AAM operators.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study addresses integrated AAM network design and demand estimation from a transportation planning perspective by determining vertiport locations at the TAZ level to maximize saved generalized costs. Airspace analysis was conducted to identify realistic AAM routes that avoid constrained airspace frequently used by commercial flights. These rerouted paths impose additional flight distance, time, and cost on AAM operations, thereby improving the realism of vertiport placement and transportation mode allocation in the study. An extended multiple allocation p-Hub median problem model was developed to integrate network design and demand estimation. Given the NP-hard nature of the problem, a novel three-part chromosome Genetic Algorithm (GA) with local search strategies was proposed and compared with a Mixed-Integer Programming (MIP) approach using Gurobi and a two-part chromosome GA from existing literature.

The methodology was applied to the extended Tampa Bay Region (TBR+), which comprises 1,521 TAZs. The TAZ-level OD matrix was obtained from the Florida Statewide Traffic Demand Model (FLSWM). For modeling purposes, vertiports were assumed to be

located at the geographic centroid of the TAZs. In the base scenario, where 30 vertiports were selected from the 1,521 candidate TAZs, the MIP solver (Gurobi) required 6,523 minutes to reach a 2.33% optimality gap, whereas the proposed 3Part-GA obtained a better solution in only 33.7 minutes. We further compared the performance of 3Part-GA with Gurobi, 2D-GA, VNS, SA, 3Part-GA without local search, and a standalone local search without a GA wrapper across multiple problem instances. The results show that 3Part-GA consistently outperformed the benchmark meta-heuristics and Gurobi for medium- and large-instances in terms of both solution quality and computational efficiency.

In the base-year scenario, the model predicts that 6,118 trips shift from ground transportation to AAM, representing approximately 0.04% of total travel demand in the TBR+ region. A factorial experimental design was employed to conduct a sensitivity analysis examining how key parameters influence the estimated level of shifted demand. Results indicate that vertiport processing time and the interaction between base air fare and the per mile flying fee have the most significant effect on AAM demand. With respect to the share of low-income travelers in total AAM demand, parking price and interaction between the per-mile flying fee and parking cost emerge as the dominant factors. Finally, the parameter with the greatest impact on access and egress travel distance is the per-mile flying fee: a one-unit increase in this parameter results in an increase of 0.305 miles in access and egress travel distance.

Several aspects of this study could be further improved. First, the airspace analysis used to construct the air link network and estimate flight time did not include a comprehensive sensitivity analysis of key parameters, such as the size of airspace cubical size and the traffic density threshold used to identify constrained regions. Incorporating insights from air traffic controllers could help better calibrate these parameters and support a more realistic airspace representation in future work. Second, the current optimization framework does not capture heterogeneity in travelers' mode choice between ground transportation and AAM and does not incorporate equilibrium effects associated with changes in roadway congestion. Instead of redefining the mode choice constraints within the E-MApHMP formulation to account for variations in traveler preferences and congestion levels, our on-going effort incorporated the deterministic E-MApHMP into an iterative algorithm by running state-wide or regional travel demand modeling for capturing the travelers

heterogeneity and the interaction between roadway mobility and introduction of AAM.

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